

Design for All

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Design Research by Under 40 Researchers

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PLAYGROUND DESIGN: AN EVALUATION TOOL FOR THE CREATION OF INCLUSIVE PLAY EXPERIENCES

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Playing in its widest meaning involves physical, sensory and social/emotional aspects. With this in mind, designing play equipment as much as possible integrated throughout and inclusive is of great social importance but also a challenging issue, especially due to the complexity of variables intervening between product requirements and user capabilities. The research work presented proposes a novel methodology for assessing the level of inclusion when designing play experiences. A cross-correlating tool based on accessibility standards and disability descriptors was developed and validated with on field experiments and interviews. This approach allows to get an immediate feedback and reliable information on the level of inclusiveness of any type of game equipment and user disability. With the final aim of designing inclusive play experiences, the developed cross-correlation tool was also exploited for supporting the creation of novel design concepts of sensory/cognitive play, which are here presented.

Keywords: Universal Design • Inclusion • playground • disability • sensory play.

Introduction

Playgrounds are historically known as places where children interact each other on different levels by experiencing and sharing multiple and diverse recreational experiences in a safe and comfortable environment. Physical, cognitive, communicative, social/emotional, and sensory interaction are the most relevant dimensions involved during playing. Inclusive playground design is therefore oriented to improve and integrate all these human dimensions with the aim to guarantee to any child the right to play with other peers regardless of any impairment and discrimination (King & Newstead, 2017) (Casey, 2010).

Community policies and global market are nowadays increasingly oriented towards the adoption of a wide range of customized solutions in support to universally inclusive play opportunities. For instance, many playgrounds are equipped with wheelchair accessible routes, transfer points, ramps, seat or basket swings, balancing bars, sensory play, nature-inspired areas and many other. With regards to sensory plays, they are considered an important element of a play space, as allow stimulating simultaneously several ability levels (i.e. tactile, auditory and visual interaction), particularly for those children with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) and sensory disabilities. There also a variety of further accommodating solutions, equipment and services, which have been designed for a wide range of abilities, activities and offer several benefits. A comprehensive classification about the range of plays divided by age groups and type of activities is displayed in Figure 1.

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Fig. 1. Play activities as classified by age groups and types of play (physical, sensory and social)¹

Thus, whenever considering play experiences the individual elements should be designed according to the principles of Universal Design (UD) and best practices. Through the engagement of children, parents, and related experts the final expected outcome should be aimed at creating equal play opportunities, positive interaction and collaborative socialization. However, despite the significant efforts, the current available solutions do not meet entirely inclusive requirements, especially for children with cognitive or physical constraints. With this perspective designers have to face with the evaluation of several

¹ **Inclusive Play Design Guide.**

<http://www.accessibleplayground.net/wpcontent/uploads/2016/05/Inclusive-Play-Design-Guide-LowRes-2.pdf>.

US Consumer Product Safety Commission: Public playground safety handbook. Government Printing Office (2010). <https://www.cpsc.gov/s3fs-public/325.pdf>.

elements whenever designing an inclusive playground facility or an individual play. From a research standpoint, the design steps are more strictly focussed on the identification and the analysis of user needs, user abilities, user product-interaction, product requirements and environmental factors. The many groups involved in promoting and delivering inclusive design solutions, from community policies to strategic planning should be taken also into account (Dong, 2015) (Clarkson & Coleman, 2015).

The representative sketch displayed in Figure 2 illustrates and summarizes all aspects to be considered. A crucial point is undoubtedly related to outline an integrated analytical strategy in order to output appropriate designing solutions and satisfy user needs throughout, by considering a plurality of physical, cognitive and social conditions. As a matter of fact, the Inclusive Design Cube, which was initially proposed for understanding the link between product demands and user capabilities, was reformulated in the area of playgrounds by adding the social dimension (Clarkson et al., 2003)(Siu & Wong, 2017). Within such a framework the main goal of the present research is to design inclusive play elements for:

- *enhancing the children's abilities on the basis of an attentive analysis of user needs*
- *fostering socialization and collaboration between disabled and non-disabled children;*
- *promoting communication among relatives and children, even in the presence of early disabilities.*

Using a purposely-developed cross-correlation tool, which helps designers to get immediate information on the level of inclusiveness, four designed concepts of play (GERDY, GOLI, SID

and DINO), developed by the LED laboratory (University of Florence, Italy), are presented.

Fig. 2. Key components for an inclusive playground design

2 Research methodology

To get preliminary information on playgrounds (i.e. dimensional and safety requirements, inclusion parameters, layout, type and quality of equipment) European and American regulatory standards were analyzed². Among the most accredited guidelines one may find: Me2: 7 Principles of Inclusive Playground Design™ (Christensen, 2010), Inclusive play design guide by Playworld,

² ASTM F1487-11 - Standard Consumer Safety Performance Specification for Playground Equipment for Public use.

ASTM F1292-09 - Standard Specification for Impact Attenuation of Surface Materials within the Use Zone of the Playground Equipment.

EN 1176-1 : Part 1: General safety requirements and test methods

EN 1176-2 : Part 2 -3: Additional specific safety requirements and test methods for swings

EN 1176-3 : Part 3: Additional specific safety requirements and test methods for slides

Let's play Toolkit³ and public playground safety handbook (Stanton et al., 2017).

Focus groups and several interviews are usually performed on to collect information about user needs, play activities, product requirements and environmental factors. These information together with the use of ICF taxonomy are used for evaluating the level of user exclusion. The classification of Figure 1 was useful for evaluating the types of play equipment installed on playgrounds and on market worldwide and to draw and plan the user needs analysis phase. Generally, for estimating the level of exclusion the following steps revealed to be essential: (1) understand the tasks when using a product within its operating environment; (2) define a specification for and collect data of a new population based on user capability; (3) calculate levels of product exclusion and difficulty; and (4) present such data in an accessible and useful way (Langdon et al., 2015) (Elton & Nicolle 2010).

To cross-correlate all the gathered information, a smart evaluation tool has been created and validated. It allows to put immediately in relation children's abilities to tasks required during play activities. The ICF classification, the international standard to describe and measure health and disability, is used for evaluating the product exclusion and the type of disability⁴. The ICF provides a tree-like classification of body function and disability composed of three lists called Body Functions, Body Structures and Activity and Participation. Furthermore, to classify contextual factors, it offers another two lists called 'Environmental Factors' and

³ *Rick Hansen Foundation, Let's Play Toolkit. Creating Inclusive Play Spaces For Children Of All Abilities Retrieved from <https://www.rickhansen.com/Portals/0/WhatWeDo/SchoolProgram/RHSPAdditional/AccessiblePlay/LetsPlayToolkit.pdf>*

⁴ *World Health Organization 2001. Retrieved from <https://www.who.int/whr/2001/en/>*

'Personal Factors'. Each domain is structured into chapters where each item can have up to four levels of depth. Thus, the ICF offers about 1500 descriptors in its taxonomy (Blasco et al., 2014).

As an example, Figure 3 shows some of the reliable disability descriptors which were selected for assessing exclusion when practicing play activities.

The disabilities taken into consideration were those corresponding to the highest levels of impairment, thus between 96 and 100% of the ICF functions qualifier. This choice was adopted to consider the most extreme level of the exclusion scale (low capability).

The level of interaction between the game and the group of users analyzed were assessed through the systematic analysis of individual games (i.e physical, sensory and social plays). For each test and sub-task identified were analyzed the levels of potential interaction, referring to specific users' physical, cognitive and sensory conditions (Clarkson et al., 2015)(Hollnagel, 2012). As an example, Fig. 3 correlates the macro-tasks of the traditional swings and of sensory games, with the level of interaction required to accomplish a specific task (Physical, Cognitive, Social).

The cross-correlation between macro-tasks and the levels of capability, as quantified by ICF descriptors, allows assessing the degree of user exclusion when performing play activities. The exclusion was evaluated in relation to the following items: (1) the user, (2) the product, (3) the environment or context (4) the activities and tasks that constitute the interaction over time.

3. Tool for assessing play inclusiveness

The developed tool displayed in Figure 3 provides an immediate feedback on the level of inclusiveness of any type of game equipment. As an example, the degree of exclusion of 5 games, namely 4 different types of swings and a sensory game, is shown. In the case of the swing evaluation, the analysis of the related tasks (i.e. access, swinging, descending phase) shows the need for support activities by an accompanying persons, especially in the presence of the physical disabilities shown in the first four lines of the Figure 3. In the case of limited or complete body functions disability (upper / lower limbs, wheelchair users), the participation of an accompanying person is strictly required for the transfer and / or for assistance activity. During the swinging phase (a.2), if there are children with severe visual and cognitive impairments, assistance and physical contact with an accompanying person is needed. However, the level of exclusion for wheelchair-bound children which cannot be transferred on remains high.

The cage swing (play in the third column) designed for children in wheelchairs, is certainly accessible for them but turns out to be a dedicated solution that excludes the participation of other children in the game activity. Moreover, these systems are dangerous and require block systems to prevent improper use of other children.

For children aged between 2 and 5 years, to increase the level of socialization, it is recommended the installation of solutions that allow the activity of swinging together with parents. Some solutions are the double seat, with the possibility of looking at each other, or the types of swing implemented with child restraint systems equipped with a backrest and side supports and safety front panels.

Therefore, the results of cross-correlation show that the most suitable swing is the shape of a basket, especially regarding the issue of socialization. This type of swing offers play opportunities to children with disabilities, who can sit or lie down, swinging alone or with other children.

For what concerns the sensory games, always illustrated in figure 3 (column 4), it has been found that they make it possible to work simultaneously on several levels, so as to better satisfy inclusion. These games help children to become aware of their senses and develop them further. These aspects are therefore of fundamental importance for the growth of cognitive, tactile, sensory-motor, social and linguistic abilities. A further positive aspect of sensory games is also due to the interaction between parents and children, as there may be cases in which the parent may reside in the disabled condition.

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Fig. 3. Cross-correlating tool showing the different types of interaction and tasks required when using traditional swings and sensory games. Age group considered 5-12 years. At the bottom, cross-correlation diagrams illustrating the matching phase between macro-tasks and degree of user exclusion/inclusion (Brischetto, Tosi & Rinaldi, 2019)

In the category of sensory play we also find sound games. In this type of games, the attention must be paid to subjects with cognitive and / or autistic disabilities. These subjects may be bothered by such games, so it is advisable to use not too high sound tones or to place, where possible, elements / materials that act as acoustic isolators. According to published studies (Muñoz, 2009) (Kaplan, 2018), almost half of the children with ASD try to move from a safe and controlled place to a more open areas. In the absence of places to shelter, half of these children tend to get lost (Gilmore et al., 2018). Therefore, solutions with shell structures or small houses may be more suitable in cases of ASD. In fact, these last solutions can have a double function, the first one concerns the possibility for ASD subjects to isolate themselves in order to observe the environment. By doing so, they can decide the most opportune moment to open up to relationships and any socialization activities. The second reason concerns the need of these subjects to identify in these structures a safe place and protection.

Another fundamental aspect for ASD subjects is to look for playgrounds that have a wide pathway around the playing area. The perimeter path is often requested by ASD children because it offers a quiet space away from the game action. It may therefore be useful to install protection systems, such as houses, tunnels or domes, near the perimeter areas. Another disturbing factor for ASD children, and in general for all children, is the presence of saturated and bright colors of the games. In addition, the flooring is important to allow the child in a wheelchair to easily reach the game and make any task required by the game. The child in a wheelchair must be able to approach the game effectively and perform the necessary actions. Moreover, the possibility of using the game by children of different height must be provided.

Usually, these games are used for learning activity, in a fun and engaging way. For instance, some fundamental notions of dynamic physics, optics and other categories of scientific knowledge can be learned. In particular the latter category of sensory games gives an active role to the player who, depending on the game, can act individually in collaboration with other players.

4. Design inclusive play experiences: the "ALL Play Together" project

The cross-correlation tool above-described revealed that play stimulating the sensory channel are the most suitable to get universally inclusive solutions and an elevated degree of socialization. Moreover, it allowed getting useful and immediate information on the types of equipment and level of interaction. Accordingly, this knowledge base supported and powered the creation of design experiments and concepts, which were carried out in collaboration with young designers.

The "All Play Together" project proposes types of play that offer many opportunities for children to feel alive and to learn in a relaxing environment. Although the planned activities may seem simple to avoid situations of failure, they have an intentional progressive difficulty. The usefulness of this method was to stimulate children to face with their skills and their senses in order to compensate the type of disability.

The "All Play together" project contains five categories of games: sound games, cognitive panels, play tables, sensory games and physical games. The inspiration for the design of cognitive panels was taken from the "puzzles". This type of games allows you to perform challenging activities that offers many benefits, such as developing fine motor skills, hand-eye coordination and memory.

The aim of these games is to improve cognitive development, as it helps children to improve imaginative strategies and to work toward a goal. In order to make these types of games accessible to children with intellectual and/or visual disabilities, tables have been designed with two surfaces, one of which is rotating and, through illustrative drawings on the surfaces, children can create a series of formal compositions. This is the case of GERDY, the concept of Figure 4 illustrating a series of round tables that encourage socialization and require a low level of muscle activity of the upper limbs. The upper rotating plate stimulates the child to find the correct combination in order to compose the body of the character to be assembled. Friendly shapes engraved on a wooden panel with the use of bright and attractive colors were created.

Fig. 4. GERDY cognitive panel. Designer: Kiana Kianfar (Project supervisors: Alessia Brischetto and Francesca Tosi)

A further cognitive game shown in Figure 4 is GOLI. It is an interactive panel characterized by four levels of difficulty, which can be overcome with the possibility of multiplying the action on the same objective. The child exercises the recognition of shapes and colors and tries to free the path to put the mobile birds in right colored location. Finally SIB and DINO (Figure 5 and 6), two cognitive panels.

SIB is a type of a play inspired by the cause-effect games and is dedicated to autistic children. Thanks to the use of hands, this game emits sounds that allow you to perceive the cause (turn) - effect (noise) that manifests when interacting with it. SIB offers the opportunity to exercise hand-eye coordination and sensory exploration. The child who comes into visual contact with another child (eye contact) socializes with it and with others. Accessibility for children in wheelchairs and also for young children has been studied. Children, regardless of their age and abilities, can interact with the side elements, as they slide on a series of tracks.

Finally, DINO is a sensory game that offers a tactile experience to children, especially for those with visual impairment. Its structure allows for the accommodation of several children at the same time, which can communicate each other and talk about their feeling by touching the panels with different textures and colors. Its shape can recall different types of animals, leaving the imagination free. Its tubular structure can be raised up from the ground and connected with other play-structures.

Fig.5 GOLI System, cognitive panel. Designer: Kiana Kianfar (Project supervisors: Alessia Brischetto and Francesca Tosi)

Fig.6 SID (top) and DINO (bottom) Systems, Designer: Kiana Kianfar (Project supervisors: Alessia Brischetto and Francesca Tosi)

5. Conclusions

The research activity herein presented focusses on the inclusive playground design giving more emphasis to sensory/cognitive play, as allow stimulating several ability levels simultaneously (i.e. tactile, auditory and visual interaction), promoting functioning development, valorizing individual diversity and collaborative socialization. Due to the complexity of variables intervening between product requirements and user capabilities, a smart cross-correlation tool was developed. The latter embeds and correlates most of the regulatory standards, systematic evaluation procedures and design best practices, aiming at facilitating and making more comparable and objective the

qualitative evaluation of play inclusiveness and accordingly, the development of integrated and inclusive design solutions. The proposed method proved to be also useful for assessing personal and environmental factors and supporting the design process along the whole working flow, from the methodological side to creational. Four sensory/cognitive systems, named GERDY, GOLLI, SID and DINO, were designed, optimized and evaluated according best practices and criteria of inclusion suggested by the cross-correlation tool.

With the aim of promoting inclusive play experiences, future research activity will be focused on testing the approach presented here on a larger population, in order to get more accurate qualitative observations regarding peers behavior in play activities.

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